

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

MODERN MILITARY COMMAND AND CONTROL SYSTEMS AND THEIR SECURITY ENSURING BASED ON THE SDN TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

In the article, a concept and architecture of a perspective military Command and Control (C2) system are proposed. Some effective algorithms and technologies for C2 systems security assuring based on cryptography there were described. The new method of the military command and control systems security ensuring efficiency assessment is described, based on using Petri Nets applications and a set of parameters such as the Reliability of Service, Defense Factor, Risk Factor, Modified Risk assessment, and the cost-effectiveness. An analytical comparison of the proposed parameters of the C2 systems security assessment based on the suggested technologies and the results of their simulation are presented.

Keywords: concept, architecture, military, command, control, system, security, assuring, assessment.

1. INTRODUCTION

Future military Command and Control (C2) systems must be designed able to adapt to a broad range of crisis and conflict situations, operate with various actors in different configurations across a full spectrum approach, and remain effective under a variety of stresses. Also, the modern C2 systems are destined to strengthen the joint force's capacity to conduct Multi-Domain Operations across the land, sea, air, space, and cyber domains.

In the article, a concept and architecture of a perspective C2 system are proposed, which includes the National, Strategic, Operational, and Tactical levels connected via a communications network to link the military headquarters across all levels of command, to provide for timely transmission of orders and directives from higher headquarters to all subordinate forces, to monitor and control the authorized military operations (section 2).

Taking into account that such kind of C2 systems has to be very robust to cyber-attacks, some effective algorithms and technologies were described for security assurance based on cryptography, proposed by the authors (section 3).

Another very important problem in the design and applications of the military C2 consists in the evaluation of the security level efficiency. In section 4 the new method is described, based on using Petri Nets applications and a set of parameters such as the Reliability of Service, Defense Factor, Risk Factor, Modified Risk assessment, and cost-effectiveness.

An analytical comparison of the proposed parameters of the C2 systems security assessment based on the suggested technologies and the results of their simulation was made in section 5.

2. MODERN MILITARY COMMAND AND CONTROL SYSTEMS

The modern military Command and Control (C2) systems must be designed able to adapt to a broad range of crisis and conflict situations, operating with various actors in different configurations across a full spectrum

approach and remain effective under a variety of conditions.

Based on the analysis of the tendencies and approaches in the development of the military C2 systems [1-16] we propose a concept of a perspective architecture that includes the National, Strategic, Operational, and Tactical levels in one network.

The national level will be represented by the Chief of the General Staff, operating under the authority and direction of the National Command Authority, the Strategic level is represented by Commanders of the Forces, Operational level is represented by the Commander of an appropriate Strategic Command, and Tactical level is represented by Commanders of Army Corps, etc.

A responsive and secure communications network will be used to link the military headquarters across all levels of command, to provide for the timely transmission of orders and directives from higher headquarters to all subordinate forces, and the timely receipt of reports, from all subordinate headquarters of the constituted military force structure, to monitor and control the authorized military operations.

The architecture is based on using different kinds of network equipment such as servers, switches, computers, etc. (Figure 1). The heart of the C2 systems is a common data network consisting of assets that enable a variety of cross-domain capabilities and devices to be seamlessly plugged in to accelerate the military's operational tempo at a rate that enemy forces cannot keep up with.

The networked capacity reduces the amount of time it takes for friendly forces to receive, fuse, and act upon a wide range of data and information from different battle domains. This involves upgrading datalinks and some space-based technologies, as well as linking sensors from several stealth platforms and drones, integrating advanced sensors and software into existing battle management command and control platforms, using the Internet Protocol, a service-oriented architecture, and developing capabilities of the Global Information Grid.

Figure 1. Network equipment used in the C2 systems

3. ALGORITHMS AND TECHNOLOGIES TO ENSURE THE SECURITY PROTECTION OF THE COMMAND AND CONTROL SYSTEMS

One of the very important requirements of the military C2 systems is to ensure a high level of security protection. By authors, there were proposed some effective algorithms and technologies for systems security assuring based on cryptography [17-19].

The algorithms suite consisted of the Hydra framework mainly and integrated within it, the secured channel of VPN algorithm, Cryptography of Double RSA algorithm, and Distributed ledger concept of Blockchain algorithm [17]. These algorithms work together and interact to form the hydra-like behavior of the framework to assure the security of the SDN structure meaning that Hydra itself is not as much as an algorithm as it is a combination of solutions and could contain some techniques as well, like the counter measurements proposed to deal with DoS/DDoS attackers by counter-attacking the attacker or attackers with botnets to control their computer/computers.

Based on the proposed algorithms, there were elaborated serial, parallel, and hybrid SDN controllers' topologies to increase the security level of network architectures, which permit the creation of a topology of SDN that contains more than one controller [18, 19].

4. THE MILITARY COMMAND AND CONTROL SYSTEMS SECURITY ENSURES EFFICIENCY IN ASSESSING

To evaluate the security level efficiency of the C2 systems we propose a new method based on using Petri Nets applications and a set of parameters which are the Reliability of Service (RoS), Defense Factor (DF), Risk Factor (RF), Modified Risk assessment (RM) and the cost-effectiveness.

Following the proposed method, at the first stage for the topology of C2 systems which are using SDN controllers, a Petri Nets model is elaborated.

In the next stage, the simulation of the elaborated model is performed using the Generalized Stochastic Petri Nets (GSPN) module which is a 6-tuple $(P, T, F, W, M_0, \lambda)$ module where, $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_m\}$ is a finite set of places $n \geq 0$, and obtaining the numerical data regarding the places and tokens.

In the third stage, to obtain data from the simulation we propose to apply a set of parameters, to evaluate the security level of computer networks.

Reliability of Service (RoS).

This parameter describes the performance reliability in data protection. RoS parameter could be close to the Quality of Service (QoS) parameter which is the definition of the performance of any system's or device's service, like a computer network or cloud computing, etc. The SDN has many positive features, which have gotten the attention of researchers to improve the QoS parameter provisioning of today's various network applications [20]. But, RoS parameter is a little bit different and of more detailed specification tailored for the needs of SDN. We propose to measure the RoS parameter as follows:

$$\text{RoS} = 1 - \text{TANT} / \text{TANT}_0, \quad (1)$$

where TANT is the Total Average Number (distribution intensity) of Tokens of the proposed topologies, which is the summation of all averages after dividing them by the count of these averages, and that could mean how many tokens per server and shows how weak or the risk occurrence level. The TANT_0 is the Total Average Number of Tokens of ordinary topology.

Defense Factor (DF).

This parameter is used to determine the strength and security feasibility of the network architecture against DoS/DDoS attacks. In terms of Petri Nets, the requests will be represented by how many tokens are there in specific places which in turn represent specific nodes in the software-defined network and those specific nodes of interest are the SDN controllers. In the equation (2, 4) places representing the SDN controllers are denoted as K , where $K \in P$, and P is the whole group of places in the Petri Nets (PN) model, which in turn is a tuple of 5 objects, $\text{PN} = \{P, T, I, O, M_0\}$, where P is the finite set of places, T is a finite set of transitions, I is the input function, O for output function and M_0 is the initial marking.

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} K_i, K_i \in \{1 - n\} \quad (2)$$

$$Z = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} Z_i, Z_i \in \{0 - \infty\} \quad (3)$$

$$DF = [\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} Ki] / [\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} Zi] = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} \left[\frac{Ki}{Zi} \right] \quad (4)$$

The parameter DF depends mainly on the assessment of the strength of software-defined network controllers based on their emptiness and that means their readiness and availability to deter any kind of DoS/DDoS attack. Therefore, it is logical to say that the more controllers we have the better the network's capability it is to deter those attacks. That means the more controllers the better and the higher DF value is and that explains why the DF equation has the places that represent the controllers in the numerator position because the amount of controllers is proportional to the value of the DF.

While on the other hand, we can see that the more tokens that represent the requests, the weaker the network gets and that means the less DF value we will get.

So, the DF value and the number of tokens or requests are inversely proportional and that's why they should be put in the denominator position. In addition, it is mentioned worthy that if we reversed the DF then, meaning if we divided the tokens/requests by the places/controllers then we'll get how many requests per server meaning; it will divide them equally and that could be unrealistic because based on the types of reactions between the controllers in every topology; a controller could be dealing with more requests while the other is just waiting as a backup controller.

Risk Factor (RF).

This parameter is used to show the weakness level of the network environment. The values of the Total Average Number of Tokens (TANT) can be described as the Risk Factor. Since we need to find the strength and defense ability of the network controllers to deter the DoS/DDoS attacks and the more tokens/ requests we have, the more occupied the controllers will be and the weaker they will be and this way we will not get defense ability or reliability level of the network but rather the weakness point.

So, we propose also the RF parameter to evaluate the efficiency of the elaborated topologies. The Parameter can be estimated as:

$$RF=1/DF, \quad (5)$$

where DF is the Defense Factor value of the measured topology. The parameter RF will still be the opposite of what we need to figure out, which is the TANT also.

Modified security Risk assessment (RM).

This parameter is used to assess the security level of networks based on the modified law of security risk assessment. We can apply the security risk assessment law [21] to evaluate the protection level of the networks, which states:

$$R=P_0*V, \quad (6)$$

where R is the security risk assessment that quantifies and shows the possibility of a threat acting upon a vulnerability successfully and the severity of the results of that attack, P_0 represents the initial probability

or likelihood of the vulnerability occurrence and V represents the value or cost of the asset.

Using the formula (6) we can estimate how much our proposed framework will reduce the security risk of a network, hence assuring its security. Since a server is the most important part and has the highest value node in the network environment, in which we will install our controller software, then we can say it has the highest asset value or impact. The servers have the value $V=100$ as an asset impact because it is the value of the server's impact on the secure socket layer (SSL) which is the same layer that the OpenFlow protocol works through.

The probability of vulnerability $P_0=0.025$ which is measured based on the lost orders due to the server denial of service attack. We can gain a new value of probability P_n , which will be affected by the DF mathematically as shown:

$$P_n=P_0/DF \quad (7)$$

The higher the Defense Factor the better which is the opposite of the probability of vulnerability, that means that they should be inversely proportional mathematically as they're logically and that's why they're positioned this way in the formula of finding the new likelihood or probability of vulnerability.

It is possible to estimate that our framework and the formula derived from its modeling, will reduce the likelihood of attacks occurrence (like DoS/DDoS attacks) and for that, we propose a modified version of the Security Risk Assessment parameter:

$$RM=P_n*V \quad (8)$$

The usage circumstances of these parameters differ from each other. When it is needed to measure the data protection performance, then it is possible to apply the RoS parameter. When there's a need to determine the defense ability and the network's strength against DoS/DDoS attacks, then it is possible to depend on the DF parameter.

While if there was a need to reverse the situation out of the weakness of the network, then it is possible to reverse the parameter and use the RF which is inversely proportional to DF. In case there was a need to measure the SDN environment weakness based on the computer networks law, then it is possible to modify it to be used based on the proposed SDN environments and their Petri Nets modeling and in this case, the RM parameter can be used.

Cost effect parameter.

To evaluate the influence of the costs of using the proposed SDN controller topologies for security assurance, we used the data regarding the prices of the basic network devices such as switches, computers, and controllers [22, 23].

For the structures of different topologies - Serial, Parallel, Hybrid, and Ordinary, let to estimate the cost of the topologies, taking into account as an example that Ordinary topology will include 1 controller, 3 switches, and 6 computers, both the Serial and Parallel topologies will have 3 controllers, 3 switches and 6

computers and the Hybrid topology will contain 6 controllers, 3 switches and 6 computers.

In this case, the total cost (TC) of the Ordinary network topology can be estimated as:

$$TC_O = CC + 3SC + 6NC \tag{9}$$

Where, CC, SC, and NC are the costs of the controller, switch, and network computer respectively. The total cost of the Serial and Parallel topologies will be as follows:

$$TC_{S,P} = 3CC + 3SC + 6NC \tag{10}$$

And the total cost of the Hybrid topology will be:

$$TC_H = 6CC + 3SC + 6NC \tag{11}$$

Let's establish the relations between the costs of the controller, switch, and computer as follows:

$$CC = aSC = bNC, \tag{12}$$

where parameters $a = \{a_{min} \div a_{max}\}$, and $b = \{b_{min} \div b_{max}\}$.

If we apply those values in the equations (9)-(11) then, the costs of the topologies could be described as:

$$TC_O = CC + 3SC + 6NC = CC(1 + 3/a + 6/b) \tag{13}$$

$$TC_{S,P} = 3CC + 3SC + 6NC = 3CC(1 + 1/a + 2/b) \tag{14}$$

$$TC_H = 6CC + 3SC + 6NC = CC(6 + 3/a + 6/b) \tag{15}$$

In summary, the effectiveness of cost difference in using the proposed topologies can be shown by the following formulas:

$$Y1 = TC_{S,P} / TC_O = 3(2a + b + ab) / (6a + 3b + ab) \tag{16}$$

$$Y2 = TC_H / TC_O = 3(2a + b + 2ab) / (6a + 3b + ab) \tag{17}$$

$$Y3 = TC_H / TC_{S,P} = (2a + b + 2ab) / (2a + b + ab) \tag{18}$$

In the last stage of the proposed method comes the analysis and interpretation of the obtained results.

5. ANALYSIS OF THE SECURITY ASSESSMENT PARAMETERS

An analytical comparison of the proposed parameters for the C2 systems security assessment based on the suggested technologies and the results of their simulation was made. The data are presented in Table 1 and Figure 2.

From these data, it is possible to infer that the Parallel topology is the best one from the point of view of all security estimation parameters, after that comes to the Serial topology and the Hybrid topology is the last one.

Table 1.

The values of RoS, DF, RF, RM, and cost for the proposed topologies

No.	Topology	RoS	DF	RF	RM	Y
1	Serial Topology	0.94	8.23	0.12	0.3	Y1 = 1.63
2	Parallel Topology	1.0	∞	0	0	Y1 = 1.63
3	Hybrid Topology	0.78	2.21	0.45	1.1	Y2 = 2.27
4	Ordinary Topology		0.5	2	5	

Figure 2. The values of RoS, DF, RF, RM, and cost for the proposed topologies

The usage circumstances of these parameters differ from each other. When it is needed to measure the data protection performance then, it is reasonable to apply the RoS parameter, and it is possible to say that the best topology of all the proposed topologies in terms of RoS, is the parallel topology.

When there's a need to determine the defense ability and the network's strength against DoS/DDoS attacks then, it is possible to depend on the DF parameter. The parallel topology has a very high value close to ∞.

While if there was a need to reverse the situation and figure out the weakness of the network then, it is possible to reverse the parameter and use the RF which

is inversely proportional to DF. It is possible to conclude that the parallel topology is 0 since it is nearly optimal and that means this structure has low risk.

After modifying the risk assessment law by incorporating the effect of the Defense Factor in its equation to create a new parameter called the Modified Risk parameter, the research shows that the parallel topology has a value of 0 as well hence, it is the best topology of all the suggested topologies.

When there's a need to see the cost-effectiveness of using the proposed topologies to assure the security of SDN paradigm as compared to the already-existing single-controller Ordinary topology; then it is possible to check the cost parameter which shows that based on our research and the specific prices' data gathered. Using Serial and Parallel topologies prices could be increased by a maximum of 1.63 times as compared to the usage of the Ordinary topology. While using the Hybrid topology could increase the expenses by 2.27 times more than the expenses for the Ordinary topology.

6. CONCLUSIONS

A concept and architecture of a perspective military Command and Control (C2) system, which includes the National, Strategic, Operational, and Tactical levels connected via a communications network to link the military headquarters across all levels of command, to provide for the timely transmission of orders and directives from higher headquarters to all subordinate forces, to monitor and control the authorized military operations, there are proposed.

Some effective algorithms and technologies for security assuring of the C2 systems, based on cryptography there were presented.

The new method of the C2 systems security level efficiency evaluation is described, based on using Petri Nets applications and a set of parameters such as the Reliability of Service (RoS), Defense Factor (DF), Risk Factor (RF), Modified Risk assessment (RM) and the cost-effectiveness.

An analytical comparison of the proposed parameters of the C2 systems security assessment based on the suggested topologies and the results of their simulation was made. We can notice that the best topology of all the described topologies will be the Parallel topology. It was established that the best DF value is for the Parallel topology as compared to the other proposed topologies and as compared to the existing Ordinary topology.

It was determined that it is possible to infer that the highest Risk Factor value is for the single-controller Ordinary topology which means that it is the weakest of all topologies. While the lowest probability value is for the Parallel topology which means that it is the best of all proposed topologies since it has the least value of vulnerability probability.

Regarding the Modified Risk parameter, the research shows that the parallel topology is the best one of all the suggested topologies.

It was concluded that the Serial and Parallel topologies would have more cost in establishing as compared to the Ordinary topology by 1.63 times and the

Hybrid topology's cost increases by 2.27 times as compared to the Ordinary topology.

The novelty of these proposed parameters stems from their basis, which is the modeling of the suggested SDN topologies using Petri Nets system to simulate their behavior and acquire numerical results from that. Based on these numerical results, those parameters were provided.

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